

A Computational Approach for Measuring Performance Quality in Violin Tones

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Background

Automatic assessment of music performance is an open and widely studied research area. Its great challenge, however, is in capturing the complexity and subjectivity of the musical material and of traditional methods of human assessment. Rather than strict, quantifiable criteria, assessment in music education relies on consensus of experts who, while highly trained, produce subjective interpretations of music performance. Even reducing musical performance to its simplest component part – the single tone – still carries these challenges. From a technical perspective, the quality of a performed sound is a result of numerous acoustic properties including pitch, loudness, and harmonic spread. The language used by musicians to describe tone, however, can be highly personal without clear parallels to the psychoacoustic properties they describe.

Aims

Our aim is twofold: (1), to understand the correlations between the human tone quality descriptors, acoustic descriptors from the literature, and the features extracted from the audio signal; and (2) to generate machine learning models to predict the different proposed quality dimensions of the performance from the audio features. The predictive models will be implemented and incorporated into a real-time feedback learning system.

Method

Perceptual tests on the quality of performed musical notes were performed using previously defined terms used in the literature to assess sound quality (i.e. pitch-dynamic-timbre stability, richness, and attack clarity), as well as a proposed list of tone qualities provided by music experts in violin education. A perceptual test to assess the quality of the performed notes was conducted. Participants were asked to mark sound quality in terms of the predefined dimensions on a 7-point Likert scale. Similarly, the proposed list of tone qualities was presented in pairs to the listener (e.g. bright/dark) to grade the sounds along a 7-point Likert scale. Low and high-level audio features were extracted from the audio signals in both temporal and spectral domains using the Essentia library. Machine learning techniques were used to generate models to predict the different quality dimensions from the extracted features.

Results

From the perceptual tests data correlation was evaluated among the different proposed perceptual sound quality dimensions. Preliminary results show that higher correlations (i.e. $CC > 0.8$) were obtained between the overall quality of the sound and pitch stability/timbre richness. Similarly, the same high correlation was found among the proposed tone qualities: grainy/pure with coarse/smooth, and restricted/free with narrow/broad. The models with best predictive accuracy were obtained for pitch stability, dynamic stability, and timbre stability. A first prototype of the real-time system for performance quality assessment was implemented, able to track pitch, dynamic, and timbre stability/accuracy.

Conclusions

A computational approach to automatically assess the quality of performed violin sounds is proposed. High and low-level descriptors were extracted from the audio signal and machine learning models were obtained to predict the different quality dimensions from the audio features. Preliminary results indicate different levels of correlation among the studied quality dimensions. Potential applications in music education settings, including those within the TELMI project, will be discussed.

Keywords

Automatic music performance assessment. Music performance modeling; Machine Learning; Violin sound quality.

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